

Applying Project-Based Learning (PBL) to Enhance Engineering Education: A Case Study on Production System Design at the University of Brasília

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Abstract

The implementation of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in engineering courses is essential to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application. This study presents an applied PBL approach in the Production System Design course at the University of Brasília (UnB), focusing on a real-world challenge faced by a recycling cooperative. The pedagogical strategy is structured in five rounds, where students progressively develop a comprehensive solution for a real industrial problem, integrating systematic problem-solving techniques, data analysis, and sustainability principles. The course methodology starts with a problem definition phase, where students conduct interviews and apply empathy maps to deeply understand the stakeholders' needs. The problem addressed in this iteration involved tracking the flow of recyclable materials at the Recicla+ Brasil cooperative, which faces operational and logistical inefficiencies. Throughout the course, students analyze the root causes using Ishikawa diagrams and the 5 Whys technique, propose solutions through a design-thinking approach, and implement prototypes tested in real conditions. Assessment is performed through rubrics for each round, evaluating problem comprehension, analytical depth, and implementation feasibility. The final round includes a technical report consolidating findings, stakeholder feedback, and a roadmap for project continuity. Results show that students develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork skills, while the cooperative benefits from structured improvements in its operations. This case study highlights the impact of active learning methodologies in engineering education and the social relevance of student-driven solutions. It also demonstrates how PBL fosters engagement, technical expertise, and a systemic perspective in addressing real industrial challenges.

Keywords: PBL; Active Learning; Sustainability; Production System Design.

1 Introduction

Engineering education is currently facing the challenge of preparing professionals capable of acting in increasingly complex, dynamic, and interdisciplinary environments. Traditional approaches, heavily based on lectures and fragmented content delivery, often fall short in developing essential skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, autonomy, and problem-solving. In response to these limitations, Active Learning methodologies have gained relevance in engineering curricula by promoting student-centered strategies that engage learners in the construction of knowledge through real-life problem-solving contexts (Decker et al., 2025; Kumar et al., 2025; Gonçalves et al., 2020; Ren et al., 2025; Junior & Goncalves, 2019).

Among active learning approaches, Project-Based Learning (PBL) stands out as an effective pedagogical strategy that bridges the gap between theory and practice. By structuring the learning process around the development of projects grounded in authentic challenges, PBL fosters not only technical competencies but also interpersonal and systemic thinking skills that are crucial for engineering professionals (Dhungana et al., 2025; Theissler et al., 2021; Shafi et al., 2018; Muideen et al., 2023; Bodenhausen et al., 2022).

This paper presents a case study from the Production System Design course at the University of Brasília (UnB), which applies a PBL methodology structured in five rounds. The project centers on a real-world problem faced

by Recicla+ Brasil, a recycling cooperative that struggles with logistical inefficiencies and lack of traceability in its operations. By engaging students in the analysis, design, and proposal of a feasible solution to this challenge, the course aimed to integrate active learning with sustainable engineering practices.

The goal of this study is to describe the pedagogical approach applied, analyze the learning outcomes for students, and reflect on the societal impact of the project. This initiative demonstrates how active learning methodologies can enhance engineering education by fostering deeper engagement, meaningful learning, and social responsibility in the training of future engineers.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Active Learning Methodologies in Engineering Education

The increasing complexity of engineering problems and the demands of the labor market have highlighted the need to reform traditional teaching models in engineering education. Active Learning has emerged as a key pedagogical approach to foster student engagement, autonomy, and the development of transferable skills such as teamwork, communication, and critical thinking. This approach shifts the focus from the teacher as the central figure to students as active agents in the learning process (Cherdo et al., 2023; Tabit et al., 2022; Jain, & Tarey, 2023; Gopalakrishnan & Kumaran, 2022; Singh, Batheri & Dias, 2023).

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is one of the most prominent forms of Active Learning in engineering education. It involves the integration of knowledge across multiple disciplines through the development of structured projects that simulate real-world challenges (Voronov, Krysander & Frisk, 2020; Redondo et al., 2020; Jain et al., 2020; Vianna et al., 2024). Unlike traditional problem-solving exercises, PBL emphasizes the process of learning by doing, encouraging students to investigate, design, prototype, and evaluate their own solutions (Gonçalves et al., 2023; Hamasaki et al., 2023; Labiod et al., 2025).

According to Shirole et al. (2025), PBL shares commonalities with other student-centered approaches like CDIO (Conceive, Design, Implement, Operate), particularly in its emphasis on interdisciplinary integration and competence development. In the PBL model, students work in teams to define problems, gather and analyze data, develop potential solutions, and reflect on their decisions and outcomes.

The pedagogical benefits of PBL are well documented in engineering literature. James et al. (2013) highlight that PBL enhances students' motivation and responsibility, promoting deeper learning and better retention of concepts. Hastie et al. (2009) also argue that PBL aligns well with the philosophical foundations of engineering education, promoting the formation of ethical, autonomous, and socially responsible professionals.

The adoption of PBL in engineering courses allows for a dynamic and reflective learning environment, where students not only acquire technical knowledge but also learn to deal with uncertainty, negotiate solutions with stakeholders, and work collaboratively under real constraints. This makes PBL particularly suitable for fostering 21st-century competencies and bridging the gap between academia and the professional world (Chen et al., 2018; Shingo, 1996; Zhang et al. 2025; de Faria et al., 2019; Zonta et al., 2020).

2.2 Sustainability and Engineering Practice

Sustainability has become a central theme in engineering education, driven by the urgent need to address environmental degradation, social inequality, and economic imbalance. Engineers today are expected not only to design efficient systems and technologies but also to contribute actively to the creation of sustainable societies. This broader responsibility requires integrating environmental, social, and economic dimensions into

the curriculum, promoting a holistic understanding of engineering solutions (Burmeister et al., 2023; Saaty, 2005; Stankevecz et al., 2019).

Incorporating sustainability into engineering education entails more than teaching environmental concepts. It involves fostering values such as social responsibility, ethical awareness, and systemic thinking. According to UNESCO's vision for sustainable development education, engineers must be equipped to design inclusive, responsible, and resilient solutions that address both human and planetary needs (Lin, Walker & Agarwal, 2025; Lourenço et al., 2023).

One of the key challenges in this integration is demonstrating to students how engineering decisions can directly influence real communities. Project-Based Learning offers a practical avenue for connecting sustainability principles with engineering practices. When students work on real-world problems—such as waste management, resource efficiency, or social inclusion—they develop a contextualized understanding of sustainability that goes beyond abstract theory (Karthikeyan et al., 2024; Prytz et al., 2015).

In the context of this study, the collaboration with Recicla+ Brasil—a recycling cooperative located in a vulnerable region of Brasília—provided students with an opportunity to engage in a socially and environmentally relevant project. The cooperative faces structural and operational challenges that limit its ability to track and process recyclable materials efficiently. By supporting the cooperative through data-driven solutions and low-cost interventions, students not only applied engineering principles but also contributed to environmental sustainability and the social inclusion of waste pickers.

This approach resonates with the concept of socio-productive sustainability, which emphasizes inclusive economic models that empower marginalized groups while promoting environmental care. Engineering education, when connected to community-based challenges, becomes a catalyst for sustainable transformation, aligning technical education with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (particularly SDG 4 – Quality Education and SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production).

3 Target Stakeholders Methodology

This research is based on a qualitative case study developed within the Production System Design course of the Industrial Engineering undergraduate program at the University of Brasília (UnB). The course adopted a Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach to connect students with a real-world challenge involving a local recycling cooperative, Recicla+ Brasil. The pedagogical structure was organized into five progressive rounds throughout the semester, each corresponding to a distinct phase of the project development process and culminating in specific deliverables and evaluations.

The first round focused on problem definition. Students conducted interviews with the cooperative's administrative staff and developed empathy maps to understand the needs, expectations, and frustrations of stakeholders involved in the recycling operation. This initial engagement enabled students to immerse themselves in the context and clearly define the central problem to be addressed—namely, the lack of traceability in the flow of recyclable materials. In the second round, students applied analytical tools such as the Ishikawa diagram (Ishikawa, 1990) and the 5 Whys technique to investigate the root causes of the inefficiencies identified. This phase fostered the development of critical and systemic thinking and supported the ideation of feasible alternatives to address the problem.

In the third round, students formulated their proposed solutions and detailed an implementation plan. The proposals were developed using design thinking principles and justified through the 5W2H method, which helped structure the "what," "why," "how," and "who" aspects of each action. The solution designed by the

group involved two complementary fronts: a physical organization system for sorting the materials based on their origin, and a digital platform for collecting and analyzing operational data through Google Forms and Looker Studio dashboards. In the fourth round, students developed a preliminary prototype of the solution and generated mock dashboards using fictitious data to simulate system behavior. Although full implementation was limited by external constraints—including loss of direct contact with the cooperative—students were able to design and validate the technical feasibility and usability of their proposed system.

Finally, in the fifth round, students consolidated their project in a technical report, which included a summary of activities, critical reflections on the process, and suggestions for project continuity. Throughout the course, the evaluation process followed a rubric-based model, with criteria assessing students' problem understanding, analytical depth, teamwork, communication, and solution feasibility. These assessments were both formative and summative, providing students with continuous feedback and opportunities for iteration.

The methodology adopted in this course promoted the integration of technical knowledge with social responsibility, enabling students to apply engineering tools in a real community setting. Furthermore, it fostered the development of essential skills such as collaboration, creativity, data analysis, and structured decision-making. The use of a real-world challenge as the core of the learning experience made the learning process meaningful, while also contributing to a broader societal impact through the potential improvement of sustainable practices within the cooperative.

4 Case Study: Production System Design Course at the University of Brasília

The application of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology was carried out in the Production System Design course offered by the Industrial Engineering program at the University of Brasília (UnB) during the second semester of 2024. The course aimed to engage students in solving a real-world problem faced by Recicla+ Brasil, a recycling cooperative located in the Paranoá region of the Federal District. The cooperative plays a central role in inclusive waste collection, environmental protection, and income generation for vulnerable populations. However, it faces operational challenges, particularly the absence of a structured system for tracking the origin and processing of recyclable materials.

The course was structured around five iterative rounds, each designed to guide students through progressive stages of project development. In the first round, students conducted interviews with the cooperative's leadership and developed empathy maps to understand the perspectives, needs, and frustrations of stakeholders. This immersion enabled the identification of key problems, including the lack of traceability of incoming materials, poor spatial organization within the warehouse, and the need for performance indicators to guide decision-making.

Building on these findings, students advanced to the second round, where they used the Ishikawa diagram and the 5 Whys technique to explore the root causes of the identified issues. The analysis revealed a combination of factors, such as limited infrastructure, insufficient formal procedures, absence of data collection mechanisms, and informal communication among staff. These elements contributed to inefficiencies in sorting, storing, and monetizing the recyclable materials.

In the third round, students proposed a solution that combined physical reorganization of the warehouse space with digital data management. The physical component involved the use of low-cost colored markers and fences to designate specific areas for materials from different collection points. This visual system aimed to simplify the sorting process and reduce material mixing. The technological component consisted of a Google

Forms-based data entry system, in which cooperative members could log key operational data such as date, number of workers, volume of material received, volume triaged, and destination of each load. The collected data was then integrated into a Google Sheets database, which powered a dynamic dashboard created in Looker Studio.

This dashboard allowed the cooperative to monitor essential performance indicators, including triage productivity per worker, volume of materials processed per day, material donation rates, and delivery schedules. Through these visual insights, cooperative managers could make more informed operational decisions, identify process bottlenecks, and optimize resource allocation.

By the final rounds, students refined their proposal and compiled a technical report presenting the full solution, supported by data visualization models and implementation strategies. The report included a 5W2H plan detailing actions, responsible parties, required resources, and proposed timelines. The proposed system aligned with the cooperative's sustainability objectives, enhanced transparency and efficiency, and contributed to the development of a data-driven operational culture.

This case study illustrates how engineering education can be enriched through real-world engagement. The experience enabled students to apply theoretical knowledge to complex, context-specific challenges, while contributing to the broader goal of socio-environmental sustainability. Moreover, the interdisciplinary nature of the problem stimulated collaboration, creativity, and a sense of social responsibility among future engineers.

5 Conclusion

The integration of Project-Based Learning (PBL) into the Production System Design course at the University of Brasilia provided valuable insights into how active methodologies can transform engineering education. Through the engagement with a real and socially relevant challenge, students experienced the full cycle of problem-solving—from understanding stakeholder needs to proposing feasible technical and organizational solutions. This approach not only reinforced academic content but also fostered the development of critical skills aligned with the demands of contemporary engineering practice, such as teamwork, analytical reasoning, communication, empathy, and decision-making under constraints.

The partnership with Recicla+ Brasil highlighted the potential of engineering education to generate positive social and environmental impacts. The proposed solution, combining physical space organization and digital data management, addressed concrete operational inefficiencies and offered a replicable model for similar cooperatives. It also introduced students to the principles of sustainability from a practical and systemic perspective, making them reflect on how engineering decisions can influence inclusive economic development, waste reduction, and social equity.

The pedagogical outcomes of the course confirmed the effectiveness of PBL in enhancing student motivation and engagement. Working on a real-world project gave meaning to the learning experience and stimulated a higher level of responsibility and initiative. The five-round structure ensured progressive immersion, while the use of design and analysis tools such as empathy maps, Ishikawa diagrams, and 5W2H planning supported structured learning. The continuous assessment model, based on rubrics and iterative feedback, allowed students to reflect on their progress and improve their deliverables across rounds (Joseph et al., 2024; Burmeister et al., 2023).

From an institutional perspective, the case reinforces the importance of building university-community partnerships that bring mutual benefits: while students gain experience and practical knowledge, local stakeholders receive innovative and tailored contributions to their operational challenges. This dynamic aligns

with the broader goals of engineering education in the 21st century, which include not only technical excellence but also social responsibility, innovation, and sustainability (Rana et al., 2024; Stankevecz et al., 2019).

In addition to the technical outcomes, the project provided valuable opportunities for students' personal and professional development. Throughout the five rounds, students reported significant learning experiences, including improvements in teamwork, communication, and the ability to apply engineering tools in real contexts. Some students highlighted the challenge of adapting theoretical knowledge to the limitations of the cooperative's operational reality, mentioning that "working with a real client made us realize the importance of listening and adjusting our proposals based on stakeholder feedback." Others emphasized the growth in critical thinking, with comments such as "understanding the root causes was not just about using tools like the Ishikawa diagram, but about questioning assumptions and validating information directly with the cooperative members." These reflections demonstrate how the PBL approach fostered not only technical competence but also a heightened sense of social responsibility and problem-solving resilience.

In conclusion, this experience demonstrates that PBL can serve as a powerful educational strategy in engineering curricula. When connected to real societal challenges, it promotes a more meaningful and holistic learning environment. The case of Recicla+ Brasil illustrates how future engineers can be agents of transformation, capable of designing solutions that are not only technically sound but also socially inclusive and environmentally responsible. The outcomes of this project point to the relevance of expanding such initiatives across engineering programs, encouraging the adoption of methodologies that place learning, context, and community at the center of academic practice.

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